

ON NEW ITERATIVE ALGORITHM FOR NUMERICAL RECKONING FIXED POINTS OF WEAK CONTRACTION MAPPING IN BANANCH SPACES AND ITS RATE OF CONVERGENCE

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Abstract

This paper introduces a novel three-step iterative algorithm designed to approximate fixed points of nonlinear self-mappings within a specific class of weak contractions in Banach spaces. Additionally, we explore and compare the convergence rates of the Mann, Ishikawa, and Noor iterative algorithms with the newly proposed one. The results indicate that the proposed algorithm achieves faster convergence compared to the aforementioned iterative methods. Furthermore, we present two numerical examples computed using MATLAB to illustrate our findings, demonstrating the approximated fixed points.

Keywords: Iterative Algorithms, Weak Contractive Condition, Rate of Convergence, Banach Theorem.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The fixed point problem is a fundamental concept in mathematics and various scientific disciplines. It involves finding a point in a given space that remains unchanged under a specified transformation or mapping. Fixed point problems have broad applications and connections across different branches of mathematics, physics, computer science, and engineering. They are often employed to solve equations, model dynamic systems, and analyze the stability of iterative processes. The existence and uniqueness of fixed points, as well as the methods to compute them, are key considerations in studying and solving problems in diverse fields. Understanding and utilizing fixed point problems play a crucial role in advancing theoretical foundations and practical applications in various scientific domains.

Approximations of fixed points play a crucial role in various mathematical contexts, offering valuable tools for solving equations, analyzing iterative processes, and understanding the behavior of dynamic systems. We can derive the approximate solutions to fixed point problems through various iteration techniques. This paper introduces a novel three-step iterative algorithm designed to approximate fixed points of nonlinear self-mappings within a specific class of weak contractions in Banach spaces.

Additionally, we explore and compare the convergence rates of the Mann, Ishikawa, and Noor iterative algorithms with the newly proposed one. The results indicate that the proposed algorithm achieves faster convergence compared to the aforementioned iterative methods. Furthermore, we present two numerical examples computed using MATLAB to illustrate our findings, demonstrating the approximated fixed point problems through various iteration techniques. In this paper, we present a three-step iterative algorithm designed to estimate the fixed points of nonlinear self-mappings under weak contractions in Banach spaces. For this, we first fix some notations and state some definitions and theorems.

Throughout the course of this paper, we adopt the assumption that C forms a nonempty convex subset within the Banach space X and T is some suitable self-mapping. In 1922, Banach [1] made a pivotal contribution to fixed-point iteration with the introduction of the Banach contraction mapping principle, abbreviated as BCP, marking a significant breakthrough. The celebrated result of Banach is:

Theorem 1.1

Let $T: X \rightarrow X$ be a contraction mapping where (X, d) is a complete metric space and $k \in (0,1)$ be contractive constant such that

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq k d(x, y)$$

for all $x, y \in X$. Then there exists a unique fixed point $x^* \in X$ for the operator T and the Picard sequence $\{x_n\}$ defined by $x_{n+1} = Tx_n$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ converges to the fixed point x^* of T .

Subsequently, numerous mathematicians have explored various iterative techniques for numerically computing fixed points across diverse classes of nonlinear mappings and within different spaces. See [2, 3, 4, 5] and references therein. Here, we present some well-known useful approximation techniques which are dedicated to seeking solutions for fixed-point problems:

In 1953, Mann [6] proposed an iterative algorithm $\{x_n^{(1)}\}$ as outlined below:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} &x_n^{(1)} \in C \\ &x_{n+1}^{(1)} = (1 - \alpha_n)x_n^{(1)} + \alpha_n T(x_n^{(1)}) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1.1)$$

for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $T: C \rightarrow C$ is a specified mapping with $\alpha_n \in [0,1]$. We note that the Picard and Krasnoselskij iterative algorithms are the particular cases of the Mann iterative algorithm (1.1). Precisely, if we take $\alpha_n = 1$ and $\alpha_n = \gamma \in [0,1]$ (constant), then the Mann iterative algorithm (1.1) reduces to the Picard and Krasnoselskij iterative algorithms respectively. The next progress in this direction was made by Ishikawa [7]. The iterative algorithm $\{x_n^{(2)}\}$ proposed by Ishikawa [7] is outlined below:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} x_n^{(2)} &\in C \\ y_n^{(2)} &= (1 - \beta_n)x_n^{(2)} + \beta_n T x_n^{(2)} \\ x_{n+1}^{(2)} &= (1 - \alpha_n)x_n^{(2)} + \alpha_n T y_n^{(2)} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1.2)$$

for all $n \in N$ and $\alpha_n, \beta_n \in [0,1]$. If we take $\beta_n = 0$, then the Ishikawa iterative algorithm (1.2) transforms into the Mann iterative algorithm (1.1). Thus, the Mann iterative algorithm is a particular instance of the Ishikawa iterative algorithm (1.2). Another progress in this direction was made by Noor in 2000. Noor [8] introduced an iterative algorithm $\{x_n^{(3)}\}$ as follows:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} x_n^{(3)} &\in C, \\ z_n^{(3)} &= (1 - \gamma_n)x_n^{(3)} + \gamma_n T x_n^{(3)} \\ y_n^{(3)} &= (1 - \beta_n)x_n^{(3)} + \beta_n T z_n^{(3)} \\ x_{n+1}^{(3)} &= (1 - \alpha_n)x_n^{(3)} + \alpha_n T z_n^{(3)} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1.3)$$

for all $n \in N$ with $T: C \rightarrow C$ is the given mapping and $\alpha_n, \beta_n \in [0,1]$. We note that iterative algorithms introduced by Mann and Ishikawa are the particular cases of the Noor iterative algorithm. More precisely, if we take $\gamma_n = 0$ then Noor iterative algorithm (1.3) transforms into Ishikawa iterative algorithm (1.1) and if we take $\gamma_n = \beta_n = 0$ then Noor iterative algorithm (1.3) transforms into Mann iterative algorithm (1.1).

Berinde [9] proposed a new contractive condition on a metric space (X, d) which is stated as follows:

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq \delta d(x, y) + L d(x, y) \quad (1.4)$$

for all $x, y \in X$ where $0 \leq \delta < 1, 0 \leq L < \infty$ and $T: X \rightarrow X$ is the given mapping. It is also called a weak contraction mapping. The condition (1.4) is called the weak contractive condition. He established that the set of weak contraction mappings is more extensive than the set of Zamfirescu mappings (see Zamfirescu mappings in [10]) He also introduced a comparative notion for the rate of convergence of two fixed points as outlined below:

Definition 1.2: Consider two sequences of real numbers $\{a_n\}$ and $\{b_n\}$ converging to a and b, respectively. Let

$$L := \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|a_n - a|}{|b_n - b|}.$$

(A₁) If $L = 0$, then we can conclude that $\{a_n\}$ converges faster to a in comparison that $\{b_n\}$ converges to b.

(A₂) If $0 < L < \infty$, then we can conclude that $\{a_n\}$ and $\{b_n\}$ converge at an identical rate.

Suppose (X, d) is a given metric space and $\{x_n\}$ and $\{y_n\}$ are two sequences in a metric space converging to the same fixed point $y \in X$ of a self-mapping T on X satisfying :

$$d(x_n, y) \leq a_n \text{ and } d(y_n, y) \leq b_n$$

for all $n \in N$ where $a_n \rightarrow 0$ and $b_n \rightarrow 0$. Subsequently, in accordance with definition (1.2), the subsequent concept emerges as inherently intuitive. If the convergence of sequence $\{a_n\}$ is faster than that of $\{b_n\}$, we state that the iteration sequence $\{x_n\}$ converges more rapidly than the iteration sequence $\{y_n\}$ toward the fixed point y . We observe that in the aforementioned definition, the assessment of the convergence rate between two iterative sequences relies on the selection of two sequences, $\{a_n\}$ and $\{b_n\}$ serving as error bounds for $\{x_n\}$ and $\{y_n\}$, respectively. In 2013, Phuengrattana and Suantai [11] observed a lack of clarity in this method. Therefore, they made modifications to Definition 1.2 specifically addressing the comparison of the convergence rates of two fixed-point iterative schemes, as outlined below:

Definition 1.3 ([11]) Consider two sequences $\{x_n\}$ and $\{y_n\}$ in a metric space (X, d) both converging to the same fixed point y of a mapping $T: X \rightarrow X$. It is asserted that $\{x_n\}$ converges faster than $\{y_n\}$ to y if and only if

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{d(x_n, y)}{d(y_n, y)} = 0.$$

In 2004, Berinde [9] also presented the following theorem.

Theorem 1.4 Let $(X, \|\cdot\|)$ be a convex Banach Space and $C \subset X$ be a nonempty closed convex set with $T: C \rightarrow C$ be weak contraction mapping on C . Then $Fix(T) := \{x \in C: Tx = x\} \neq \emptyset$. Furthermore, the Picard iteration sequence $\{x_n\}$, also converges to a fixed point of T .

This paper presents a novel iterative algorithm designed for discovering fixed points of weak contraction mappings in Banach spaces, inspired by the aforementioned algorithms. We conduct a comparison of the convergence rates between our proposed iterative algorithm and the Mann, Ishikawa, and Noor iterative algorithms. We propose the following three step iterative algorithm:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} x_1 &\in C, \\ z_n &= T((1 - \gamma_n)x_n + \gamma_n T x_n) \\ y_n &= (1 - \beta_n)x_n + \beta_n z_n, \\ x_{n+1} &= (1 - \alpha_n)x_n + \alpha_n T y_n \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1.5)$$

where $\alpha_n, \beta_n, \gamma_n \in [0, 1]$. We will show that the new iterative scheme (1.5) converges at a faster rate compared to the other iterative algorithms mentioned, specifically for weak contraction mappings.

In Section 2, initially, we will establish the convergence result of the proposed iterative algorithm (1.5) to approximate the fixed point of T in X . Subsequently, we will assess and compare the convergence rates of Mann (1.1), Ishikawa (1.2) and Noor (1.3) algorithms with our iterative algorithm (1.5). In Section 3, we will provide some numerical computation examples to illustrate our main result.

2 MAIN RESULTS

To begin with, we will establish the convergence theorem for the iterative algorithm (1.5) designed to approximate the fixed point of a weak contraction mapping in Banach spaces. Furthermore, we will demonstrate that our newly proposed iterative algorithm converges at a faster rate compared to the Mann (1.1) Ishikiwa (1.2), Noor (1.3) iterative algorithms when applied to weak contraction mappings in Banach space.

Theorem 2.1. Let $(X, \|\cdot\|)$ be a Banach Space and let $C \subset X$ be a closed and convex. Let $T: X \rightarrow X$ be a mapping satisfying the contractive condition (1.4) as outlined below. There exist $0 \leq \delta' < 1$ and $0 \leq L' < \infty$ such that for all $x, y \in X$

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq \delta' d(x, y) + L'd(x, Tx) \tag{2.1}$$

Let $\{\alpha_n\}, \{\beta_n\}, \{\gamma_n\}$ be sequences in $[0, 1]$ satisfying $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \alpha_n = \infty$. Then x_n defined in equation (1.5) converges to the singular fixed point of the operator T .

Proof: Theorem 1.4 ensures the existence of a fixed point of T . Additionally, the statement in (2.1) asserts that T possesses a unique fixed point. Let y be the unique fixed point T . We will show that the sequence $\{x_n\}$ in (1.5) converges to y . Using (1.5), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|x_{n+1} - y\| &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)x_n + \alpha_n T y_n - y\| \\ &\leq (1 - \alpha_n)\|x_n - y\| + \alpha_n \delta' \|y_n - y\| \\ &= (1 - \alpha_n)\|x_n - y\| + \alpha_n \delta' \|(1 - \beta_n)Tx_n + \beta_n z_n - y\| \\ &\leq (1 - \alpha_n)\|x_n - y\| + \alpha_n (1 - \beta_n) \delta' \|x_n - y\| + \alpha_n \beta_n \delta' \|z_n - y\| \\ &\leq \{(1 - \alpha_n) + \alpha_n (1 - \beta_n) \delta'^2\} \|x_n - y\| + \alpha_n \beta_n \delta'^2 \|(1 - \gamma_n)x_n + \gamma_n T x_n - y\| \\ &\leq \{(1 - \alpha_n) + \alpha_n (1 - \beta_n) \delta'^2\} \|x_n - y\| + \alpha_n \beta_n (1 - \gamma_n) \delta'^2 \|x_n - y\| + \alpha_n \beta_n \gamma_n \delta'^3 \|x_n - y\| \\ &= \{1 - \alpha_n [1 - \delta'^2 + \beta_n \gamma_n \delta'^2 - \beta_n \gamma_n \delta'^3]\} \|x_n - y\| \\ &\leq \{1 - \alpha_n (1 - \delta'^2)\} \|x_n - y\| \\ &\vdots \\ &\prod_{k=1}^n \{1 - \alpha_k (1 - \delta'^2)\} \|x_1 - y\| \end{aligned}$$

for every n . It gives

$$\|x_{n+1} - y\| \leq \prod_{k=1}^n \{1 - \alpha_k (1 - \delta'^2)\} \|x_1 - y\| \tag{2.2}$$

for every n . Using the fact that $e^x \geq 1 + x$ for $x \geq 0$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \|x_{n+1} - y\| &\leq \prod_{k=1}^n e^{-\{\alpha_n(1-\delta'^2)\}} \|x_1 - y\| \\ &= e^{-\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \{\alpha_n(1-\delta'^2)\}} \|x_1 - y\| \end{aligned} \quad (2.3)$$

for every n. By letting n approach to infinity in equation (2.3) and applying the condition $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \alpha_n = \infty$, we conclude that the expression $\|x_{n+1} - y\|$ tends to zero and the proof is completed.

Theorem 2.2. Let $(X, \|\cdot\|)$ be a Banach Space and let $C \subset X$ be a closed and convex. Let $T: X \rightarrow X$ be a mapping satisfying the contractive condition (1.4) given by: there exist $0 \leq \delta' < 1$ and $0 \leq L' < \infty$ such that for all $x, y \in X$

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq \delta' d(x, y) + L' d(x, Tx) \quad (2.4)$$

Let $\{\alpha_n\}, \{\beta_n\}, \{\gamma_n\}$ be sequences in $[0, 1]$ satisfying $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \alpha_n = \infty$. Suppose the sequences $\{x_n^1\}, \{x_n^2\}, \{x_n^3\}$ are as in equations (1.1), (1.2), (1.3) respectively. Then the sequences $\{x_n^1\}, \{x_n^2\}, \{x_n^3\}$ converge strongly to a unique fixed point of T.

Proof: The statement from Theorem 1.4 ensures the existence of a fixed point for T. The uniqueness of fixed point of T is guaranteed by (2.4). Let us denote the unique fixed point of T by y . We will show that the sequence $\{x_n\}$ in (1.3) converges to y . Using (1.3), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|x_n^{(3)} - y\| &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)x_n^{(3)} + \alpha_n T y_n^{(3)} - y\| \\ &\leq (1 - \alpha_n) \|x_n^{(3)} - y\| + \alpha_n \delta' \|y_n^{(3)} - y\| \\ &= (1 - \alpha_n) \|x_n^{(3)} - y\| + \alpha_n \delta' \|(1 - \beta_n)x_n^{(3)} + \beta_n T z_n^{(3)} - y\| \\ &\leq (1 - \alpha_n) \|x_n^{(3)} - y\| + \alpha_n \delta' (1 - \beta_n) \|x_n^{(3)} - y\| + \alpha_n \beta_n \delta'^2 \|z_n^{(3)} - y\| \\ &= \{1 - \alpha_n (1 - \delta' (1 - \beta_n))\} \|x_n^{(3)} - y\| + \alpha_n \beta_n \delta'^2 \|(1 - \gamma_n)x_n^3 + \gamma_n T x_n^3 - y\| \\ &\leq \{1 - \alpha_n (1 - \delta' (1 - \beta_n))\} \|x_n^{(3)} - y\| + \alpha_n \beta_n \delta'^2 (1 - \gamma_n) \delta'^2 \|x_n^3 - y\| \\ &\quad + \alpha_n \beta_n \gamma_n \delta'^3 \|x_n^3 - y\| \\ &= \{1 - \alpha_n (1 - \delta' (1 - \beta_n) - \delta'^2 \beta_n (1 - \gamma_n) - \delta'^3 \beta_n \gamma_n)\} \|x_n^{(3)} - y\| \\ &= \{1 - \alpha_n (1 - \delta' (1 - \beta_n) - \delta'^2 \beta_n (1 - \gamma_n + \delta' \gamma_n))\} \|x_n^{(3)} - y\| \\ &= \{1 - \alpha_n (1 - \delta' (1 - \beta_n) - \delta'^2 \beta_n (1 - (1 - \delta') \gamma_n))\} \|x_n^{(3)} - y\| \\ &= \{1 - \alpha_n (1 - \delta' + \delta' \beta_n - \delta'^2 \beta_n (1 - (1 - \delta') \gamma_n))\} \|x_n^{(3)} - y\| \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \{1 - \alpha_n (1 - \delta' + \delta' \beta_n (1 - \delta' (1 - (1 - \delta') \gamma_n))\} \|x_n^{(3)} - y\| \\
 &\leq (1 - \alpha_n (1 - \delta')) \|x_n^{(3)} - y\| \\
 &\vdots \\
 &\prod_{k=1}^n (1 - \alpha_n (1 - \delta')) \|x_1^{(3)} - y\|
 \end{aligned}$$

for every n. It implies that for every n,

$$\|x_n^{(3)} - y\| \leq \prod_{k=1}^n (1 - \alpha_n (1 - \delta')) \|x_1^{(3)} - y\| \tag{2.5}$$

Using again $e^x \geq 1 + x$ for $x \geq 0$, we obtain for every n,

$$\|x_n^{(3)} - y\| \leq \prod_{k=1}^n e^{-(1-\delta')\alpha_n} \|x_1^{(3)} - y\| = e^{-(1-\delta') \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_n} \|x_1^{(3)} - y\| \tag{2.6}$$

By letting n approach to infinity in equation (2.3) and using the condition $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \alpha_n = \infty$, we conclude that $\|x_n^{(3)} - y\| \rightarrow 0$, that is, the sequence $\{x_n^{(3)}\}$ in (1.3) converges to an unique fixed point of T. By the similar process, we can prove that the sequences $\{x_n^{(1)}\}$, $\{x_n^{(2)}\}$ generated by (1.1) and (1.2)

converge to the unique fixed point of T and then the proof is concluded.

Next, we investigate the rate of convergence of our new proposed iterative scheme (1.5) together with Mann (1.1), Ishikawa (1.2) and the Noor (1.3) iterative algorithms.

Theorem 2.3. Let $(X, \|\cdot\|)$ be a Banach Space and let $C \subset X$ be a closed and convex. Let $T: X \rightarrow X$ be a mapping satisfying the contractive condition (1.4) given by: there exist $0 \leq \delta' < 1$ and $0 \leq L' < \infty$ such that for all $x, y \in X$

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq \delta' d(x, y) + L' d(x, Tx) \tag{2.7}$$

Suppose that $\{x_n^{(1)}\}, \{x_n^{(2)}\}, \{x_n^{(3)}\}$ and $\{x_n\}$ are generated by (1.1), (1.2), (1.3) and (1.5) respectively. Let $\{\alpha_n\}, \{\beta_n\}, \{\gamma_n\}$ and $\{\alpha_n + \beta_n\}$ be a sequence in $[0, 1]$ with $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \alpha_n = \infty$ satisfying:

(C₁) there exists η satisfying $0 < \eta < \alpha_n \beta_n < 1$ for every $n \in N$;

(C₂) $0 < \alpha_n < \frac{1}{1+\delta'}$ for every $n \in N$;

(C₃) $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \alpha_n = 0$,

Then the sequence x_n in (1.5) converges faster than Mann (1.1), Ishikiwa (1.2), and Noor (1.3) iterative algorithms to a fixed point of T.

Proof: From Theorem 2.1 and 2.2, the sequence that $\{x_n^{(1)}\}$, $\{x_n^{(2)}\}$ and $\{x_n^{(3)}\}$ generated by (1.5), (1.1), (1.2) and (1.3) respectively, converges to a unit fixed point of T . Assume that $y \in \text{Fix}(T)$. First of all by using the weak contractive condition (1.4) and the Noor iterative algorithm (1.3), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|x_{n+1}^{(3)} - y\| &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)x_n^{(3)} + \alpha_n T y^{(3)} - y\| \\
 &\geq (1 - \alpha_n) \|x_n^{(3)} - y\| - \alpha_n \|T y_n^{(3)} - y\| \\
 &\geq (1 - \alpha_n) \|x_n^{(3)} - y\| - \alpha_n \delta' \|y_n^{(3)} - y\| \\
 &= (1 - \alpha_n) \|x_n^{(3)} - y\| - \alpha_n \delta' \|(1 - \beta_n)x_n^{(3)} + \beta_n T z_n^{(3)} - y\| \\
 &\geq (1 - \alpha_n) \|x_n^{(3)} - y\| - \alpha_n (1 - \beta_n) \delta' \|x_n^{(3)} - y\| - \alpha_n \beta_n \delta'^2 \|z_n^{(3)} - y\| \\
 &= (1 - \alpha_n (1 + (1 - \beta_n))) \|x_n^{(3)} - y\| - \alpha_n \beta_n \delta'^2 \|(1 - \gamma_n)x_n^{(3)} + \gamma_n T x_n^{(3)} - y\| \\
 &\geq (1 - \alpha_n (1 + (1 - \beta_n))) \|x_n^{(3)} - y\| - \alpha_n \beta_n (1 - \gamma_n) \delta'^2 \|x_n^{(3)} - y\| \\
 &\quad - \alpha_n \beta_n \gamma_n \delta'^3 \|x_n^{(3)} - y\| \\
 &= (1 - \alpha_n (1 + \delta' (1 - \beta_n (1 - \gamma_n (1 - \delta'))))) \|x_n^{(3)} - y\| \\
 &\geq (1 - \alpha_n (1 + \delta')) \|x_n^{(3)} - y\| \\
 &\vdots \\
 &\geq \prod_{k=1}^n (1 - \alpha_k (1 + \delta')) \|x_1^{(3)} - y\| \tag{2.8}
 \end{aligned}$$

For all $n \in N$. From (2.2) and (C_1) , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|x_{n+1} - y\| &\leq \prod_{k=1}^n (1 - \alpha_k \beta_k (1 - \delta'^2)) \|x_1 - y\| \\
 &\leq (1 - \eta (1 - \delta'))^n \|x_1 - y\| \tag{2.9}
 \end{aligned}$$

for every n . Subsequently, we will demonstrate that the sequence x_n defined in (1.5) converges more rapidly than the. Noor iterative algorithm (1.3) to a fixed point of T . From (2.8) and (2.9), we obtain

$$\frac{\|x_{n+1} - y\|}{\|x_{n+1}^{(3)} - y\|} \leq \frac{(1 - \eta (1 - \delta'))^n}{\prod_{k=1}^n (1 - \alpha_n (1 + \delta'))} \tag{2.10}$$

For all $n \in N$. Let $\theta_n = \frac{(1-\eta(1-\delta'))^n}{\prod_{k=1}^n(1-\alpha_n(1+\delta'))}$ for all $n \in N$. By the assumption that $0 < \alpha_n < \frac{1}{1+\delta'}$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \alpha_n = 0$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\theta_{n+1}}{\theta_n} &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{(1-\eta(1-\delta'))^{n+1}}{\prod_{k=1}^{n+1}(1-\alpha_n(1+\delta'))} \frac{\prod_{k=1}^n(1-\alpha_n(1+\delta'))}{(1-\eta(1-\delta'))^n} \\ &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{(1-\eta(1-\delta'))}{(1-\alpha_{n+1}(1+\delta'))} = (1-\eta(1-\delta')) < 1. \end{aligned}$$

By the ratio test, we obtain $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \theta_n < \infty$. So, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \theta_n = 0$. Based on the Definition 1.2, it can be inferred that the sequence $\{x_n\}$ given in (1.5) converges more rapidly than the Noor iterative scheme (1.3) to a unique fixed point of T. Also, from the weak contractive condition (1.4) and using Ishikawa iteration (1.2), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|x_{n+1}^{(2)} - y\| &= \|(1-\alpha_n)x_n^{(2)} + \alpha_nTy^{(2)} - y\| \\ &\geq (1-\alpha_n)\|x_n^{(2)} - y\| - \alpha_n\|Ty_n^{(2)} - y\| \\ &\geq (1-\alpha_n)\|x_n^{(2)} - y\| - \alpha_n\delta'\|y_n^{(2)} - y\| \\ &= (1-\alpha_n)\|x_n^{(2)} - y\| - \alpha_n\delta'\|(1-\beta_n)x_n^{(2)} + \beta_nTz_n^{(2)} - y\| \\ &\geq (1-\alpha_n)\|x_n^{(2)} - y\| - \alpha_n(1-\beta_n)\delta'\|x_n^{(2)} - y\| - \alpha_n\beta_n\delta'^2\|z_n^{(2)} - y\| \\ &= (1-\alpha_n(1+(1-\beta_n)))\|x_n^{(2)} - y\| - \alpha_n\beta_n\delta'^2\|(1-\gamma_n)x_n^{(2)} + \gamma_nTx_n^{(2)} - y\| \\ &\geq (1-\alpha_n(1+(1-\beta_n)))\|x_n^{(2)} - y\| - \alpha_n\beta_n(1-\gamma_n)\delta'^2\|x_n^{(2)} - y\| \\ &\quad - \alpha_n\beta_n\gamma_n\delta'^3\|x_n^{(2)} - y\| \\ &= (1-\alpha_n(1+\delta'(1-\beta_n(1-\gamma_n(1-\delta')))))\|x_n^{(2)} - y\| \\ &\geq (1-\alpha_n(1+\delta'))\|x_n^{(2)} - y\| \\ &\quad \vdots \\ &\geq \prod_{k=1}^n(1-\alpha_k(1+\delta'))\|x_1^{(2)} - y\| \end{aligned} \tag{2.11}$$

For all $n \in N$. From (2.2), (C_1) and (2.11), we obtain

$$\frac{\|x_{n+1} - y\|}{\|x_{n+1}^{(2)} - y\|} \leq \frac{(1-\eta(1-\delta'))^n}{\prod_{k=1}^n(1-\alpha_n(1+\delta'))}$$

For all $n \in N$. Let $\theta'_n = \frac{(1-\eta(1-\delta'))^n}{\prod_{k=1}^n(1-\alpha_n(1+\delta'))}$ for all $n \in N$. By the assumption that $0 < \alpha_n < \frac{1}{1+\delta'}$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \alpha_n = 0$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\theta'_{n+1}}{\theta'_n} &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{(1-\eta(1-\delta'))^{n+1}}{\prod_{k=1}^{n+1}(1-\alpha_n(1+\delta'))} \frac{\prod_{k=1}^n(1-\alpha_n(1+\delta'))}{(1-\eta(1-\delta'))^n} \\ &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{(1-\eta(1-\delta'))}{(1-\alpha_{n+1}(1+\delta'))} \\ &= (1-\eta(1-\delta')) \\ &< 1. \end{aligned}$$

By the ratio test, we obtain $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \theta'_n < \infty$. So, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \theta'_n = 0$. According to Definition 1.2, it can be inferred that the sequence x_n given in (1.5) converges faster than the Ishikawa iterative algorithm (1.2) to a unique fixed point of T . Finally, from (1.4) and using Mann iterative (1.1), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|x_{n+1}^{(1)} - y\| &= \|(1-\alpha_n)x_n^{(1)} + \alpha_n T y^{(1)} - y\| \\ &\geq (1-\alpha_n)\|x_n^{(1)} - y\| - \alpha_n \|T y_n^{(1)} - y\| \\ &\geq (1-\alpha_n)\|x_n^{(1)} - y\| - \alpha_n \delta' \|y_n^{(1)} - y\| \\ &\geq (1-\alpha_n(1+\delta'))\|x_n^{(1)} - y\| \\ &\vdots \\ &\geq \prod_{k=1}^n(1-\alpha_k(1+\delta'))\|x_1^{(1)} - y\| \end{aligned} \tag{2.13}$$

For all $n \in N$. From (2.2), (C_1) and (2.13), we obtain

$$\frac{\|x_{n+1} - y\|}{\|x_{n+1}^{(1)} - y\|} \leq \frac{(1-\eta(1-\delta'))^n}{\prod_{k=1}^n(1-\alpha_n(1+\delta'))}$$

For all $n \in N$. Let $\theta''_n = \frac{(1-\eta(1-\delta'))^n}{\prod_{k=1}^n(1-\alpha_n(1+\delta'))}$ for all $n \in N$. By the assumption that $0 < \alpha_n < \frac{1}{1+\delta'}$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \alpha_n = 0$, This gives

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\theta''_{n+1}}{\theta''_n} &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{(1-\eta(1-\delta'))^{n+1}}{\prod_{k=1}^{n+1}(1-\alpha_n(1+\delta'))} \frac{\prod_{k=1}^n(1-\alpha_n(1+\delta'))}{(1-\eta(1-\delta'))^n} \\ &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{(1-\eta(1-\delta'))}{(1-\alpha_{n+1}(1+\delta'))} \end{aligned}$$

$$= (1 - \eta(1 - \delta')) < 1.$$

Utilizing the ratio test, we obtain $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \theta_n'' < \infty$. So, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \theta_n'' = 0$. Based on Definition (1.2) it can be inferred that the sequence x_n in (1.5) converges more rapidly than the Mann iterative algorithm (1.1) to a fixed point of T .

3 NUMERICAL RESULTS

This section provides two numerical examples to illustrate our results. In both examples, our iterative algorithm (1.5) converges faster than the Mann iterative algorithm (1.1), Ishikawa iterative algorithm (1.2) and also the Noor iterative algorithm (1.3).

Example 3.1. Let $C = [0; 4] \subset R$ and a mapping $T : C \rightarrow C$ be defined by

$$T(x) = \frac{(2x^3 + x + 1)^{\frac{1}{4}}}{2}$$

For all $x \in C$. Choose $\delta' = 0.5$, $\alpha_n = \frac{1}{2n}$, $\beta_n = 0.2 + (-1)^n 0.1$, $\gamma_n = 0:98$ for all $n \in N$. By the mean value theorem, T satisfies the weak contractive condition (1.4). Obviously, the sequences $\{\alpha_n\}$, $\{\beta_n\}$, and $\{\gamma_n\}$ satisfy all the conditions of Theorem 2.3. With an arbitrary initial point $x_1 = 0.6$, the values of our corresponding iteration (1.5), the Mann iteration (1.1), Ishikawa iteration (1.2) and Noor iteration (1.3) are given in Table 1. Thus, it is easy to see that our iterative algorithm converges faster than the Mann, Ishikawa and the Noor iterative algorithms. Also, we give the convergence behaviors of these iterations via graphs in Figure 1.

Table 1: Comparative results of Example 1

Step	Mann Iteration	Ishikawa Iteration	Noor Iteration	Our Iteration
2	0.598483916494721	0.598448735817006	0.598449439314256	0.598124681632967
3	0.598017003284587	0.597956606052301	0.597957804485687	0.597628439195979
4	0.597765520955629	0.597707215138744	0.597708369461453	0.597379005980161
5	0.597601065845144	0.597537331100425	0.597538587529671	0.597220233822371
6	0.597482140291969	0.597420664790368	0.597421875240599	0.597109375380264
7	0.597390652314582	0.597327036883473	0.597328286050202	0.597025066529711
8	0.597317256565651	0.597255516132444	0.597256727510014	0.596959133211789
9	0.597256561010337	0.597193779862770	0.597195009204710	0.596904903176999
10	0.597205201147200	0.597143974653084	0.597145172830904	0.596859967462983
...	...	...	...	...
996	0.596245082766654	0.596220359608070	0.596220822228672	0.596140478844406
997	0.596245009020367	0.596220290953233	0.596220753472159	0.596140437239272
998	0.596244935376484	0.596220225358915	0.596220687725087	0.596140396044598
999	0.596244861834761	0.596220156896963	0.596220619161697	0.596140354562610
1000	0.596244788394954	0.596220091486747	0.596220553599108	0.596140313489744

Figure 1: The convergence behaviors of the iterations given in Example 3.1

Now we consider another example:

Example 3.2. Let $C = [0,10] \subset R$ and $T: C \rightarrow C$ be a mapping such that

$$T(x) = \cos(\sin x)$$

Take $\delta' = 0.1$, $\alpha_n = \frac{0.9}{n}$, $\beta_n = 0.08 + (-1)^n 0.01$ and $\gamma_n = 0.99$ for all $n \in N$. Employing mean vale theorem, one can show that T satisfies the weak contractive condition (1.4). It is obvious that the sequences of $\{\alpha_n\}$, $\{\beta_n\}$, an $\{\gamma_n\}$ satisfy all the conditions of Theorem 2.3. With an arbitrary initial point $x_1 = 1$, our corresponding iterative algorithm (1.5), the Mann iteration (1.1), Ishikawa iteration (1.2) and the Noor iteration (1.30 are given in Table 2. Thus, it can easy to see that our iterative algorithm converges faster than the Mann, Ishikawa and the Noor iterative algorithms. Also, we give the converges behaviors of these iterations in Figure 2.

Step	Mann iteration	Ishikawa iteration	Noor iteration	Our iteration(Eq. Sh)
2	0.699730070853593	0.708301286807801	0.708214577336960	0.829237583810303
3	0.744713764658499	0.746025151672159	0.746009395561991	0.806800704317861
4	0.754993155639641	0.755416542938301	0.755410604139427	0.797414528172676
5	0.759323591370664	0.759433954622046	0.759431626178641	0.792045973325332
6	0.761649227251321	0.761656493759896	0.761655498755227	0.788566173196360
7	0.763077675863320	0.763024187149373	0.763023992816200	0.786070344743696
8	0.764033791622552	0.763959192760659	0.763959345304906	0.784207001402784
9	0.764713280457026	0.764622262384837	0.764622677659200	0.782735266227993
10	0.765218022870076	0.765123596280576	0.765124119860581	0.781556056824028
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
996	0.768163218271131	0.768161423468437	0.768161442749288	0.768602590645365
997	0.768163226108057	0.768161433251018	0.768161452511698	0.768602271220458
998	0.768163233926790	0.768161443105194	0.768161462344574	0.768601954748160
999	0.768163241727392	0.768161452843380	0.768161472062670	0.768601636431079
1000	0.768163249509922	0.768161462652881	0.768161481850958	0.768601321055266

Figure 2: The convergence behaviors of the iterations given in Example 3.2

4 CONCLUSION

This paper introduces a novel three-step iterative algorithm designed to approximate fixed points and analyzes the performance of the algorithm. The convergence behavior of the algorithm, based on the newly proposed fixed-point iterative scheme (1.5), is explored under specific conditions applied to the control parameters. The study delves into the convergence rate of the proposed iterative scheme in comparison with other schemes. Additionally, two numerical examples are presented to demonstrate the reliability of the control parameters in our results. The findings indicate that the sequence $\{x_n\}$ generated by the proposed iterative scheme (1.5), achieves faster convergence to the fixed point compared to the Mann iteration (1.1), the Ishikawa iteration (1.2), and the Noor iteration (1.3) based on the number of iterations.

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